

8T and Cluster Decomposition

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Abstract:

In this paper, an analysis of the cluster decomposition will be made as part of a Lorentzian manifold, (M, g_E) with signature (3,1). The manifold is a connected manifold, $M = M_0 \times R$, invoked stationary. The analysis will be made based on the version of the principle as presented in quantum field theory, in which it requires that, the connected part of the S matrix, $S_{\beta\alpha}^C$ to vanish.

Introduction

In quantum field theory, one learns that the connected part of the S matrix must vanish. Distinct events do not effect each other.

$$S_{\beta\alpha}^C \rightarrow 0 \quad (1)$$

What is the equivalent of the cluster decomposition principle on the Lorentz manifold (M, g_E) with signature (3,1), invoked stationary, $M = M_0 \times R$, is the subject of this paper.

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad - \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.11)$$

Since the manifold experience arbitrary variations that vanish into matter, all across the metric, the smoothness of the metric must be taken into account. Bosonic propagation described by the delta must cross the metric before reaching a distinct event on the manifold. The result of such a construction would be that only arbitrary variations that vanished relatively closed to each other, will have an effect on each other. Suppose we had two distinct arbitrary variations, that is by discretizing and partitioning the term δg in equation (1.11), as was done in previous papers of the 8T, to proof that these are fermions:

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$\delta g = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.21)$$

We impose two conditions equivalent to the cluster decomposition in QFT. Those conditions are synonymous with saying that distinct events will not affect each other. Consider two arbitrary variations

$$\delta g_i + \delta g_{i+1} \quad (2)$$

Suppose those appeared at distinct parts of the metric, M_μ is a four vector isomorphic to the arbitrary variation with the matching index δg_i :

$$M_\mu \rightarrow M(x_i, y_i, z_i, t_i) \quad (2.1)$$

$$\delta g_i \rightarrow M_\mu$$

Same for the additional variation, δg_{i+1} , a four vector M_ν , the condition then requires that:

$$M_\mu - M_\nu \leq \epsilon \quad (2.11)$$

$$\epsilon \rightarrow 0$$

In other words, two arbitrary variations must appear close to each other on the metric, at very short time interval. That is synonymous with the quantum field theory statement of the connected part of the amplitudes to vanish. The two conditions are synoptic in the four vector. The arbitrary variations should appear close on the metric spatial dimensions and at a short time interval.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)